

DEVELOPMENT OF GYMNASTICS IN THE POST-INDEPENDENCE PERIOD.

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Annotation: This article provides information about the periods of development of gymnastics in the post-independence period and the athletes who contributed to their development in the history of gymnastics.

Аннотация В данной статье представлена информация о периодах развития гимнастики в период после обретения независимости и о спортсменах, внесших свой вклад в их развитие в истории гимнастики.

Gymnasts and coaches of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan are making great progress in new conditions. Our athletes are thoroughly preparing to test their strength on international sports fields. This made it possible for Uzbek athletes to independently participate in the World and Olympic Games. Uzbek gymnasts O. Chusovitina, R. Galieva took part in the World Championships in gymnastics and won a gold medal. At the 1996 Olympic Games, O. Chu-sovitina, A. Dzyundziak, I. The Valievs took a place among the top 10 leagues in gymnastics all-around.

The Sports Gymnastics Federation was established in Uzbekistan and accepted by the International Gymnastics Federation (FIJ).

O. at the Asian Games held in Hiroshima. Chusovitina won 2 bronze medals in pole vault and double pole.

In the competitions held in Bangkok in 1998, E. Gordeeva, A. Dzyundziak, B. Bayatanova, S. Bahriddinova, O. Skilled athletes such as Chu-sovitina took part. Today in the republic R.G. Sarkisov, R.S. Tsirkin, A. Qualified sports coaches like Olushev are working. Among the women's Olympic reserves, V. Ochilova, N.

Almatova, F. Khojaeva, A. Kambekova, R. Nasibulina, A. Habibrahmonova, from men A. Markelov, I. Valiev, A. Fokin, A. Karimjonov, R. Ailov, K. Hasanov, I. Athletes like Rahmatov grew up.

Representatives of the Gymnastics Federation of Uzbekistan participate in FIJ and Asian Association conferences. All work is carried out in cooperation with the Ministry of Culture and Sports Affairs, NOC. Committee meetings are held regularly, issues of approval of national team members, achievements of athletes in the held competitions are discussed. Work is carried out with sponsors who provide funds for leading athletes to participate in international competitions.

Today, the gymnastics federation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and people who spare no effort for the development of this beautiful sport are making their contribution. Skilled gymnasts O. Chusovitina, N. Dzyundzyak, S. who serves to improve the skills of their followers. Kuznetsova and other well-known coaches are their teachers V. Vnuchkova, G. Petrov, V. Aksenov, Z. Bondarenko, V. Kurland, R. Using the heritage left by the Sarkisovs, they are raising the sports glory of our country in international competitions.

National champions

Йиллар	Еркаклар	Аёллар
1990	Р.Галимов	З.Хайдарова
1991	Б.Залядский	О.Айбиндер
1992	А.Бадуров	И.Панкова
1993	Р.Галимов	С.Нинкова
1994	Ш.Мамадалиев	А. Дзюндзяк
1995	А.Илюшенко	Б.Баятанова
1996	Т.Курбонбоев	А. Дзюндзяк
1997	Т.Курбонбоев	С. Бахриддинова
1998	И.Валеев	С. Бахриддинова
1999	И.Валеев	А.Гордеева
2000	И.Валеев	О. Чусовитина
2003	И.Валеев	О. Чусовитина

2004	А.Фокин	О. Чусовитина
2005	А. Фокин	Н.Алматова
2006	И.Раҳматов	Н. Алматова
2007	А.Фокин	А.Нинкова
2008	Р.Осимов	Л.Галиулина
2009	А.Фокин	Л.Галиулина
2010	А.Фокин	Л.Галиулина

Gymnastics at the Olympic Games

Gymnastics was included in the first program of the new era Olympic Games. However, its format differs from the current program of gymnastics sports competitions.

1896 - Athens (Greece). 10 countries participated in the 1st Olympic Games, 5 of them participated in the gymnastics competition.

In doubles — 18 participants from 3 countries: 1st place A. Flatov (Germany), 2nd place J. Sutter (Sweden), 3rd place X. Weinghortner (Germany) won. Between teams from 2 countries

67 participants took part, Germany took 1st place, Greece-1 team took 2nd place, Greece-2 team took 3rd place.

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